

MACROSCOPIC MODELLING OF DAMAGE PROCESSES IN THERMOSTRUCTURAL COMPOSITE MATERIALS

P.M. Lesne, J.F. Maire, J.L. Chaboche

ONERA BP 72 - 92322 CHATILLON CEDEX, France - Fax ; 33 1 46734143

ABSTRACT

The paper develops a Continuum Damage Mechanics model for Ceramic Matrix Composites, that use damage variables both related to microcracks oriented by the constituents and microcracks oriented by the loading. The advantages and difficulties of the approach are discussed. We focuss particularly on simulations for both tensile and compressive loading at 0° and 45° of fiber directions.

1 - INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of composite materials in many applications needs the development of structure computational tools that incorporate both the various material non-linearities, and pertinent failure criteria. Depending of the different scales to be considered and of the general trends of the used matrices, several typical non linear behaviours could take place, including viscoelastic non linear/viscoplasticity for organic matrix composites, plasticity for MMC's. However, a common trend is the development of microcracking and microdebonding that produces both a typically elastic damaging behaviour associated to a progressive elastic stiffness reduction.

In this paper we present the development of a Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) model and their application for Ceramic Matrix Composites (C/SiC and SiC/SiC). The material has a 2D microstructure, without stratification aspects. The superposed plies have the same directions so that we can consider at some scale as a macroscopic 3D continuum. Moreover the main non linearities are associated with brittle damage effects (microcracking or microdebonding) so that the material is assumed to be elastic with damage, neglecting the hysteretic effects. The irreversible strains are described through the introduction of a residual stress state (related to the manufacture process).

The aim of this paper is to present our modeling development, as applied to SiC/SiC and C/SiC composites, some simulations of tension/compression loadings and to discuss the possible modifications of damage criterion. The present theory is developed elsewhere [1][2]. The model is written here in their small strains/isothermal/rate independent form.

2 - THE GENERAL FRAMEWORK

The present CDM theory is based on the classical thermodynamic framework, in which we may introduce two potentials :

The thermodynamic potential, that renders the state law. It depends upon the observable variables and on the damage internal state variables. We use here the Gibbs free

enthalpy $\psi^* = \psi^*(\sigma, d_\alpha)$. The thermodynamic variables $\varepsilon = \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial \sigma}$ and $y_\alpha = -\frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial d_\alpha}$ are

obtained by classical derivation where d_α represents the family of damage variables and y_α plays the role of an elastic energy release rate [3]. Let us note that the thermodynamic state potential contains all informations to describe the present damaged state. The behaviour is elastic but damaged, we have possibility of damage induced anisotropy, as well as irreversible strains associated to damage. Moreover the damage can be active (open microcracks) or inactive (closed microcracks) depending on the sign and direction of the applied loading (stress or strain) relative to the present damage (directions of the existing microcracks).

The dissipation potential. The damage growth is assumed here to be the only dissipative process. In order to be thermodynamically consistent, we need to check the second principle, that reduces in the present isothermal case to the positivity of the product between the y_α and damage rate. In this paper, we adopt the standard procedure that consider the existence of a dissipation potential, written in the generalized space of the thermodynamic forces y_α . We assume here the existence of a non-damaging surface $f < 0$ (in the y_α space) so that any state inside the surface is not producing further damage. Damage increases ($f = 0$) take place only if y_α

is on the surface and if the loading condition takes place, that is if $\sum_\alpha \frac{\partial f}{\partial y_\alpha} \dot{y}_\alpha \geq 0$. Then damage rate $\dot{d}_\alpha = \dot{\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial y_\alpha}$. The damage multiplier $\dot{\mu}$ is determined, in the rate independent case, by the consistency condition $f = 0$ in generalized normality condition.

3 - FORMULATION OF THE MODEL

3.1. Choice of the damage variables

In the Ceramic Matrix Composites, damage results essentially from matrix microcracks or interface decohesions that change the macroscopic elastic response through changes of elastic stiffness or compliance tensors. Two kinds of damage variables will be considered :

- *scalar variables*, associated with the initial directions of the constituents (fibers, yarns), of the composite. They correspond to microcracks that are oriented mainly by the microstructure : parallel or perpendicular to the fibers, especially for woven composites. Here, we assume an initial orthotropy of the material and three scalar damage variables (proportional to the microcrack densities) associated with each of the principal directions of the initial orthotropy : δ_1 and δ_2 reduce the corresponding Young's moduli in the directions 1 or 2 of the yarns in a woven structure, δ_3 applies for the direction perpendicular to the plies.

- *tensorial variables*, associated with microcracks that have been oriented by the damaging loading. These microcracks are often observed in the cmc's for both SiC/SiC and C/SiC woven composites [4]. Though a fourth rank damage tensor could be more appropriate to describe a general induced anisotropy [5][6][7] we limit ourselves to a second rank tensor d

3.2. The damage effect tensors

In order to introduce the effect of damage on the present elastic behaviour of the material we adopt the notion of a fourth order damage effect tensor, that acts on the compliance tensor through additive rule. For instance, we choose to write the damaged compliance tensor, with all damage active (all microcracks open) as equation (2) in Table I.

The compliance variation is decomposed in two terms : the first one introduces for each scalar damage δ_i a fourth order damage effect tensor A_i that expresses with the directions p_1, p_2, p_3 of

Table 1 : Equations of model

■ **State Potential :**

$$\psi^* = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma : S^o : \sigma + \bar{\sigma} : \Delta S^{eff} : \bar{\sigma}) \quad \bar{\sigma} = \sigma - \sigma^o \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta \bar{S} = + \sum_{i=1}^3 \delta_i [A_i : H_i]_s \cdot [D(d) : H]_s \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta S^{eff} = \Delta \bar{S} - \eta_1 \sum_{i=1}^3 h(-p_i : \bar{\sigma} : p_i) \delta_i P_i : [A_i : H_i]_s : P_i$$

$$\eta_2 \sum_{i=1}^3 h(-n_i : \bar{\sigma} : n_i) N_i : [D(d) : H]_s : N_i \quad (3)$$

$$\Lambda_1 = p_1 \otimes p_1 \otimes p_1 \otimes p_1 + \alpha_{12} [(p_1 \otimes p_1) \otimes (p_2 \otimes p_2)]_s + \alpha_{13} [(p_1 \otimes p_1) \otimes (p_3 \otimes p_3)]_s$$

$$\beta_{12} [(p_1 \otimes p_2)_s \otimes (p_1 \otimes p_2)_s] + \beta_{13} [(p_1 \otimes p_3)_s \otimes (p_1 \otimes p_3)_s] \quad (4)$$

$$D(d) = \alpha [1 \otimes d]_s + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \alpha) [1 \otimes d + d \otimes 1 + d \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes d] \quad (5)$$

■ **State Equations :**

$$\epsilon = S^o : \sigma + \Delta S^{eff} : \bar{\sigma} \quad (6)$$

$$y_i = \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial \delta_i} = \frac{1}{2} \bar{\sigma} : [A_i : H_i]_s : \bar{\sigma} - \frac{1}{2} \eta_1 h(-\text{Tr}(\sigma_i^*)) \sigma_i^* : [A_i : H_i]_s : \sigma_i^*$$

$$\text{with } \sigma_i^* = P_i : \bar{\sigma} \quad (7)$$

$$y = \frac{\partial \psi^*}{\partial d} = \frac{1}{4} \alpha [\text{Tr}(\bar{\epsilon}) \bar{\sigma} + \text{Tr}(\bar{\sigma}) \bar{\epsilon}] + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \alpha) (\bar{\sigma} \cdot \bar{\epsilon})$$

$$- \eta_2 \sum_i h(-\text{Tr}(\sigma_i^*)) \left\{ \frac{\alpha}{4} [\text{Tr}(\bar{\epsilon}_i^*) \sigma_i^* + \text{Tr}(\sigma_i^*) \bar{\epsilon}_i^*] + \frac{1 - \alpha}{2} (\sigma_i^* \cdot \bar{\epsilon}_i^*) \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{with } \bar{\epsilon} = S^o : \bar{\sigma} \quad \sigma_i^* = N_i : \bar{\sigma} = \bar{\sigma}_{n_i} (n_i \otimes n_i) \quad \bar{\epsilon}_i^* = S^o : \sigma_i^*$$

■ **Scalar Damage :**

$$f_i = \langle y_i \rangle - r_i (\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3) \leq 0 \quad (9)$$

■ **Tensorial Damage :**

$$f = \|y\| - r(\|d\|) \leq 0 \quad (10)$$

S^o initial compliance, ΔS^{eff} this variation with damage ; h Heavyside's function ;
 σ stress tensor ; σ^o residual state stress tensor ; ϵ strain tensor ;
 δ_i scalar variables, d damage tensor (rank 2) ; $N_i = n_i \otimes n_i \otimes n_i \otimes n_i$; $P_i = p_i \otimes p_i \otimes p_i \otimes p_i$;
 n_i directions of scalar damage (initial anisotropy axis) ; p_i principal directions of damage tensor
 $\eta_1, \eta_2, H_i, H, \alpha_{12}, \alpha_{13}, \beta_{12}, \beta_{13}, \alpha$ are scalar parameters of model

the constituents, with equation (4) and similar ones by circular permutations. When the constituents are mutually orthogonal, the case assumed here, the damage effect tensor can be expressed in a matrix form (see ref [8]). For the tensorial damage, which evolution is driven by the present loading conditions, the damage effect tensor is expressed in closed form through classical tensorial products ($C=A \otimes B : C_{ijkl}=A_{ij} B_{kl}$; $C=A \otimes B : C_{ijkl}=A_{ik} B_{jl}$; $C=A \otimes B : C_{ijkl}=A_{il} B_{jk}$). Let us note the unique degree of freedom, the material dependent coefficient α . The tensors H and H_i are chosen here as S^0 the initial compliance. Others possibilities exist as a_i^l (see ref [2] for details).

3.3. Damage evolution and deactivation

For the damage evolution equations (table III), we follow the standard procedure and the corresponding normality rules. A dissipation potential is assumed to exist and is assimilated with the damage loading surface (that enclose all the non-damaging states) expressed in the space of the thermodynamic forces y_i and Y associated to the damage state variables δ_i and d .

Damage can be active or inactive depending on the related direction and sense of the present loading conditions leading to a partial or complete closure of the corresponding microcracks (the unilateral closure effect). The damage deactivation procedure used in the present models was proposed first in [11]. It is physically motivated by the independent closure of each system of microcracks, submitted to its own local independent strain (or stress). We use the normal stress or strain, associated to the microcrack direction as an indicator of the crack opening/closing. When the normal stress or strain is negative, the corresponding normal compliance (normal to the crack) recovers its initial undamaged value (partially or completely, depending on parameter η). The key of the proposed condition is to leave unchanged the non-diagonal stiffness terms (or compliance) as well as the shear moduli. Providing this choice, both the symmetry of the effective compliance tensor S and the continuity of any stress-strain response are preserved.

4 - NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

The model presented have good capabilities to describe the classical test conditions for materials like SiC/SiC or C/SiC [1] [8] [11]. In ref [2] we gave an other formulation of the model who give the same good capabilities. The simulations presented on figures 1, 2, 3 concern woven C/SiC composites [7]. The present simulation use a linear evolution of damage parameters for equations (9) and (10) with associated variables (Q is a second rank tensor) :

for the scalar damage :

$$\langle y_i \rangle = \sqrt{\sum_i (y_i)^2} \quad \text{and} \quad r_i = a(\delta_1 + \delta_2 + \delta_3) + b \quad (11)$$

for the tensorial damage: $\|y\| = \sqrt{\text{trace}(Q.y.y.Q)}$ and $r(\|d\|) = x \text{trace}(d) + y$ (12)

Only a saturation effect of damage parameters is more imposed. On figure 1 experimental results are compared with numerical simulations for tension-compression at 0° . It is important to remark that damage increase only for the positive part of the loading. The unilateral damage deactivation effect is correctly modelled without any discontinuity on the stress-strain response. On bottom of figure 1 crack density are simulated to show the directionality of damage. In this present case we verify the coincidence of cracks induced by both scalar and tensorial variables. The residual strains, associated to damage, are described without introducing any additional dissipation, through the notion of residual internal state given by σ_0 in eqs (1) for which the damage deactivation takes place.

Figure 2 and 3 present respectively tension and compression at 45° of fiber direction. It is worthnoting that compression induced less damage than tension with respect to experimental results. In compression the tensorial damage is not activated while scalar damage increase due

Figure 1 ; Tension-compression at 0 degree. Stress-strain simulation and experience

Figure 2 : Tension test at 45 degrees. Stress-strain and damage evolution

Figure 3 ; Compression at 45 degrees. Stress-strain and damage evolution

to shear stress. In tension both scalar and tensorial damage are activated and reconstitute the non linearity of stress-strain curve. The scalar damage is due to microcracks parallel to fibers of the woven fabric, as indicated on the bottom of figures, while the tensorial damage induces cracks perpendicular to stress direction (here direction 1).

5 - CONCLUDING REMARKS

A constitutive model of the macroscopic behaviour of brittle composite systems have been briefly recalled, based on the framework of CDM. Other formulation of the model with their capabilities and deficiencies is detailed in a recent paper [2]. Nevertheless it appears that :

- the models are quite good for describing most of the experimental observations under simple loading conditions : tension, compression, torsion...

- some difficulties are related to the use of a restricted deactivation rule particularly for shear moduli (to meet continuity requirements) and of the standard thermodynamic format. Some ways of improvement are actually explored for further modeling studies in the light of recent analytic conditions [12].

- new damage criteria must be evaluated and more complete multiaxial testing studies performed in order to improve the description of the coupling of loading directions.

- this class of model have already applications for both metallic and organic matrix composites and also for the creep-fatigue damage of single crystal superalloys [13].

6 - REFERENCES

- [1] Maire, J.F., Lesne, P.M., Chaboche, J.L. : "Une nouvelle formulation de la mécanique de l'endommagement pour les composites". Submitted to "La Recherche Aérospatiale".
- [2] Chaboche, J.L., Lesne, P.M., Maire, J.F., "Macroscopic modelling and damage processes in CMC's", HTCMC2 Santa Barbara, 21-24 Aug 1995.
- [3] Chaboche, J.L., 1977 : "Sur l'utilisation des variables d'état interne pour la description du comportement viscoplastique et de la rupture par endommagement", Symposium Franco-Polonais de Rhéologie et Mécanique, Cracovie.
- [4] Aubard, X., 1992 : "Modélisation et identification du comportement mécanique des matériaux composites 2D SiC-SiC : Thèse Paris VI.
- [5] Chaboche, J.L., : "Development of CDM for Elastic Solids Sustaining Anisotropic and Unilateral Damage", Int. J. of Damage Mechanics, vol. 2, 1993.
- [6] Lubarda, V.A., Krajcinovic, D., "Damage tensors and the crack density distribution", Int. J. Solids Structures, vol. 30, pp.2859-2877, 1993.
- [7] Lesne, P.M., Saanouni, K., : "Modelling of irreversible Damage-induced Strains in Brittle Elastic Composites", La Recherche Aérospatiale, 1993-2.
- [8] Chaboche, J.L., Lesne, P.M., Maire, J.F., Phenomenological Damage Mechanics of brittle materials with description of unilateral damage effects, US-Europe Workshop on Fracture and Damage, Prague, septembre 1994.
- [9] Chaboche, J.L., 1992 : "Damage Induced Anisotropy : On the Difficulties Associated with the Active/Passive Unilateral Condition", Int. J. of Damage Mechanics, 1(2), pp. 148-171.
- [10] Chaboche, J.L., 1992 : "A new Unilateral Condition for the Description of Material Behaviour with Anisotropic Damage", C.R. Acad. Sci., Paris, t.314, série II, p.1295-1401.
- [11] Chaboche, J.L., Lesne, P.M., Maire, J.F. : "Macroscopic Modelling of Inelastic and Damage Processes with Unilateral Effects in Composite", ASME WAM, Chicago, nov. 1994.
- [12] Kachanov, M. Elastic solids with many cracks and related problems, "Advances in Applied Mechanics, ed. J. Hutchinson and T. Wu, vol. 30, Academic Press, New York, 1993.
- [13] Gallerneau, F. "Etude et modélisation de l'endommagement des superalliages monocristallins pour aubes de turbine", Thèse Ecole des Mines de Paris to be published 1995.